

**DESIGN OF READINESS MODEL FOR
INDUSTRY 4.0 IMPLEMENTATION IN
INDIAN ENGINEERING INDUSTRIES**

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1. Introduction

Industry 4.0 is the new trend among the academic and Industry. It depicts a new era of the 4th Industrial revolution because of the advances in the field of ICT [1]. The organizations around the world are getting digitally transformed due to “vertical”, “horizontal” and “end-to-end integration” of the organization to form a flexible, agile and efficient digital ecosystem, which is productive and highly competitive in global markets [2]. There is no universally accepted definition of Industry 4.0, a definition of Industry 4.0, which has more relevance to Industrial Engineering, due to the value creation and strategic reasoning is by Picarozi et al., (2019) wherein they defined “*Industry 4.0 refers to the integration of Internet of Things technologies into industrial value creation enabling manufacturers to harness entirely digitized, connected, smart, and decentralized value chains able to deliver greater flexibility and robustness to firm competitiveness and enable them to build flexible and adaptable business structures, [acquiring] the permanent ability for internal evolutionary developments to cope with a changing business environment as the result of a purposely formulated strategy implemented over time*”[3]. One of the central concepts which underpin Industry 4.0 is “smart manufacturing”. This is achieved by using strategic design of cyber-physical systems along with the integration of entire elements of the supply chain and the product life cycle [4]. Manufacturing has seen a sea change due to the technological breakthroughs such as “Cyber-Physical systems (CPS)”, “Internet of Things (IoT)”, “cloud computing”, and “additive manufacturing” . CPS leads to an agile and dynamic production environment which results in “efficiency” and “effectiveness” of the organization. From a technical perspective Industry, 4.0 is the amalgamation of various technologies such as “IoT”, “cloud manufacturing”, “Radiofrequency identification”, “Enterprise resource planning”, and “social product development” [5]. Industry 4.0 is devoted to connecting the physical world in the organization with the virtual world using technological concepts such as “embedded systems”, “semantic machine to machine communication”, IoT and CPS[6]. A modern production process should deal with ever-increasing needs of the customer, thus it becomes a complex “digital ecosystems” which is interconnected with stakeholders. Consequently, the “smart factory” concept integrates both the cyber and physical systems dynamically to meet the customer needs. Besides, Industry 4.0 implementation models suggests “horizontal”, “vertical” and “end-to-end integration” [7]. “Horizontal integration” can be thought of as digital

integration of all value creators of products who are external to the organization. It creates a holistic integration of value networks, which enables collaboration between various organizations in the value chain to meet the needs of an organization. The successful manufacturing of products is possible when organization cooperates, coordinates, and collaborates with other participating organization in the value chains leading to a new efficient and agile “digitized supply chain”.

The “vertical integration” can be thought of as the integration of various hierarchical subsystems within the organization. This integration helps to create a flexible, “reconfigurable manufacturing system”, agile, efficient, effective and safe functioning of the organization to meet the ever-increasing customer needs [8]. The informational subsystems with various functional departments within the organization are connected to a cyber system. This integration results in a network of “smart machines” or digital hierarchical departments within the organization, which will function in a self-regulating, autonomous, and intelligent manner using data-based decision making to create various products & services. The generation of big data due to the vertical integration is managed efficiently using algorithms within the organization to carry out day to day tasks within the organization.

The “end-to-end engineering” integration, is the integration of various phases of the product life cycle. This results in an ability for organizations to create customized products and services across the value chain. A chain of activities must be digitalized to create a product-centred value creation process. For example, the digital integration of customer needs analysis, product design and development, production, services, maintenance, and recycling will create an interconnected, coordinated, and cooperative networks within the organization structure which will help to deal with modern organizational problems. Such integration will result in the creation of "customized", "automated", "self -organized", low cost, high-quality products and services to meet the needs of the modern customers [9]. The basic motivation for the organization to implement Industry 4.0 is "technology application push" and "technology application pull". The "technology application push" is driven by the advances in ICT such as IoT, CPS, Cloud Computing, Additive manufacturing, digitalization of organization etc. The “technological application pull” is the need of the market in terms of reduction in the product development time, increased personalization, demand for smart products, high-quality products, digital customer service etc [10]. Industry 4.0 is thus beneficial for

customer, organization and other stakeholders[2]. However, many organizations are still not clear about the “effect and impact” of Industry 4.0[11]. There is also uncertainty as regards to what is Industry 4.0. One study suggests that there are 12 design principles and 14 technologies which are fundamental for the implementation of Industry 4.0 [12]. Another study suggests that 64 technologies are the fundamental requirement for the implementation of Industry 4.0[13]. This conceptual and technological uncertainty creates difficulty for organizations to implement Industry 4.0. There are also reports which suggest that the initial cost of implementing Industry 4.0 is very high. A technological limitation which is highlighted as a major disadvantage is interoperability or compatibility between IT systems [14]. Industry 4.0 has, however, received a tremendous response from both the Government and Industry. Among the 10 global forerunners of Industry 4.0, India is the only middle-income country which is aspiring digital transformation of Industries[15]. The “SAMARTH Udyog Bharat 4.0” an initiative from the “Government of India” is a strategic initiative in this regard. This programme by the “Government of India” is to help Indian Industries to use these advanced technologies of Industry 4.0, to make products and services which can be sold in the global markets[16, 17]. The Indian Engineering Industries represent the biggest segment in the Indian Industry. It is also India’s largest foreign exchange earner, as it contributes to 25% to Indian total exports in goods. It further has 30% weight in India’s “Index of Industrial Production” [18]. The engineering industries being labour & capital-intensive, the application of Industry 4.0 will make them efficient, effective, productive, and cost-efficient which will, in turn, lead to “competitive advantages” in both internal and external markets. Before the application of Industry 4.0, Indian Engineering Industries must assess whether they are ready to implement Industry 4.0 or in other words the existing predisposition of the firm is conducive for the effective implementation of Industry 4.0. In a generic perspective, Industry 4.0 readiness could be described as “how an organization is poised to utilise the Industry 4.0 technologies to its benefits” [10]. In other words, is the organization in a position to utilise the Industry 4.0 technologies to meet their goals and objectives. The ability of the organization will also depend on the context and as well as in the region where it is located. In a contextual sense, the challenges an organization faces in heavy engineering segment will be different from the textile industry. Similarly, the challenges in terms of location, the implementation in India would be different than in Europe because of socio-economic, technological, cultural factors. Internet connectivity in India is a challenge, especially in rural areas. If

the organization is in rural areas of India, the large amount of data which needs to be transmitted over industrial ethernet would be a herculean task. In 2019, India was ranked 79th in the network readiness index[19]. A second challenge would be the huge initial investment for Indian Engineering Industries. This is especially difficult when the exports of engineering goods from India dropped by 6.2% in the year 2019-20. Besides, the performance in March 2020, has been dismal due to Covid-19 pandemic[18]. During these challenging times finding the initial investment for implementing Industry 4.0 would be a challenge. Another challenge would be taking into confidence the trade unions. Also, the existing workforce may feel threatened by automation and they may fear they will be made redundant in the due course. Organizations must strategically deal with the trade union to convince them of its socio-technical benefits [20]. Cybersecurity is another aspect organizations fear because Industry 4.0 implementation will put sensitive information about the organization's products and services online[21]. Miscreants can hack the information to create an undue advantage for some firms or create undue loss to the host firm. The skill requirement in Industry 4.0 is more polarised towards ICT and traditional engineering disciplines will have to orient core engineering skills towards ICT [22]. Thus, there is a pertinent need to examine the Industry 4.0 readiness factor in the context of Indian Engineering Industries.

2. Research Problem

In a recent survey by Rajnai & Kocsis [23], some leaders from Industry expressed that they have not even heard about Industry 4.0. However, some leaders knew about it, but they did not know what exactly Industry 4.0 is and how to implement it. In India, very few manufacturers have implemented Industry 4.0 [24] and the general awareness of Industry 4.0 is dismally poor[25]. Industry 4.0 professes digitalization of hierarchical subsystems within and external to the organization and thus, it leads to transforming an organization. It is changing the strategy, business models, operations and in other words changing the overall organization. This is a big decision for an organization to undertake. Therefore, organizations should at first ascertain, whether they are ready to implement Industry 4.0. This could be done using simple self-assessment instruments. However, most of the self-assessment models are devoting to studying organization IT readiness[26]. Nevertheless, Industry 4.0 implementation is beyond technological component, as it is joint optimization of socio-technical systems[8]. Some of the Industry 4.0 models are PwC maturity model of Industry 4.0, Industry 4.0 maturity model

developed by ACATECH study and the Forrester digital maturity model which captures the complexity and maturity of the digital transformation of enterprises in four dimensions. A thematic analysis of these models transpires that the assessment dimensions conceptually differ from model to model. Furthermore, none of these models offers any generic and widely accepted methodology for assessing the Industry 4.0 readiness for organizations [27]. Previous researchers have studied Industry 4.0 readiness models [10, 27]. However, the vast majority of the Industry 4.0 readiness models are less “pragmatic” in terms of the rapidly advancing objectives of the organizations [10]. Industry 4.0 readiness models are important for the organizations as it will help in understanding the present position of the organization and the change that is required for the application of Industry 4.0. In the Industry 4.0 implementation sense, it can be seen as a management tool, which will help in realignment, reconfiguration and renewal of organizations capabilities and capacities [28]. Furthermore, the application of Industry 4.0 will result in the creation of new business models, strategies, KPI etc [10, 29]. Thus, it is pertinent to understand the dimensions of Industry 4.0 as regards to its dimensionality and contextual significance. Besides, Industry readiness factors will differ between developing and developed countries [30]. Indian Engineering Industries being the highest foreign exchange earner, implementation of Industry 4.0 will help the nation, industry, stakeholder, and society. This sector also employs a sizable number of Indian workforce and if Indian Engineering Industry becomes globally competitive it will lead the country to become a global superpower. Indian Engineering exports have dropped 6.16% in the year 2019-2020. The exports have dropped from US\$ 80.95 billion in 2018 to US\$ 75.97 in 2019. Due to COVID -19 pandemic, the exports have further declined in 2020 by 22%[18]. The Indian Engineering Industries to be globally competitive must make the products smart, implement Industry 4.0, improve quality, mass production, customization, be agile and efficient to meet global market needs. Hence, implementation of Industry 4.0 assumes strategic importance for the country as well for the Indian Engineering Industry. As Industry 4.0 is making gradual inroads to Indian Engineering Industry, there is a need for a comprehensive study which first explore the factors which identify the key dimensions for Industry 4.0 readiness and then subsequently develop an Industry 4.0 readiness model to implement Industry 4.0

3. Objectives & Research Question for the Study

The main objective of this study is to conceptualise and design an Industry 4.0 readiness model which can be used by the Indian Engineering Industries to assess the readiness of Industry 4.0.

The sub Objectives underlying this study would be

1. To assess the dimensions of “Industry 4.0 readiness models” for “Indian Engineering Industries”.
2. To develop an “Industry 4.0 readiness” measuring system for “Indian Engineering Industries”.
3. To statistically evaluate the “Industry 4.0 readiness model” for “Indian Engineering Industries”.

The research questions in this study are

1. What are the dimensions used to assess the Industry 4.0 readiness for “Indian Engineering Industries”?
2. How to measure Industry 4.0 readiness for “Indian Engineering Industries”?
3. How efficient is the proposed Industry 4.0 model to measure the readiness for Indian Engineering Industries?

4. Materials & Methods

This study used a sequential mixed method design wherein first a systematic literature review and a qualitative study would be used to explore the factors and subsequently quantitative method will be used to develop a model to measure the Industry 4.0 readiness. A sequential design is adopted in this study because in the first phase of using qualitative study explore those factors or dimensions of Industry 4.0 in the Indian Engineering Industry setting. In the second phase, using a quantitative study the researcher intends to develop and test the Industry 4.0 readiness model [31]. Structural Equation Modelling would be used to ascertain the readiness of the tool using confirmatory factor analysis.

5. Conclusions

Industry 4.0 or more commonly known as the fourth industrial revolution has digitally transformed the modern organization using technologies such as IoT, Cloud Computing,

Additive Manufacturing and CPS. The machine to machine communication along with IoT has transformed the organization using improved communication, self-monitoring and smart manufacturing which can transform modern manufacturing into agile, flexible, and fully automated digital ecosystem. Industry 4.0 is making a gradual inroad in Indian Industries. One of the largest segments in the Indian Industry is Indian Engineering Industries. It is one of the largest exporters and biggest foreign exchange-earners. The implementation of Industry 4.0, in Indian Engineering Industry, will transform it into globally competitive and capable of dominating the global markets. However, Industry 4.0 is technologically very complex, expensive, and cumbersome to implement. There are no tools to understand how ready an organization is before implementing Industry 4.0 in the Indian context. This study thoroughly conducts a literature review on Industry 4.0 readiness model. Using a qualitative study, this study unearths the ten dimensions of Industry 4.0 readiness model. These ten dimensions were used to design an Industry 4.0 readiness model for Indian Engineering Industries. A survey was conducted on 212 senior managers from Indian Engineering Organization using the designed scale. An exploratory factor analysis was conducted for measurement purification. First and second-order confirmatory factor analysis was conducted to confirm the dimensionality and to demonstrate the higher-order construct of Industry 4.0 readiness model. The internal consistency of the scale was tested using Cronbach Alpha and was found to be acceptable. Test-retest reliability was also conducted and found that the scale is stable over the period. The Industry 4.0 readiness model for Indian Engineering Industry was conceptualised, designed and validated using the scale development process. Further, a scoring instruction system was designed using the Industry 4.0 readiness model. The model can be used to find the overall readiness of the organization, as well as it can be used to assess the individual dimensions.

6. Significance of the Study

This study will contribute to academia in three-fold. First, it will help to explore the readiness factors for the successful implementation of Industry 4.0 in the Indian Engineering Industry. Secondly, it will provide a cogent tool to measure Industry 4.0 readiness for various firms in Indian Engineering Industry. Third, it will provide with academia a statistically validated tool which will help the academicians to measure Industry 4.0 readiness and advance the body of knowledge on Industry 4.0 readiness. The organizations can further use this tool to describe, prescribe and compare Industry

4.0 readiness before implementing Industry 4.0 in their organizations. The organization can also use this tool to evaluate their readiness in various dimensions and use appropriate measures to improve the score in those lagging dimensions strategically in those areas so that Industry 4.0 measures becomes a success.

7. Disposition of the Thesis

Chapter 1 is devoted to introduction where the concept of Industry 4.0 would be discussed along with research problem, objectives & research question, materials & methods, and significance of the study

Chapter 2 is devoted to the review of the literature on Industry 4.0. It begins by demystifying what is Industry 4.0, exploring the Pros and Cons of Industry 4.0 from an organization perspective, how the organizations and Governments around the world have responded towards Industry 4.0. Industry 4.0 is formally defined and various research approaches in Industry 4.0 is analysed. Subsequently, the review advances towards Indian Engineering Industries and Industry 4.0, Engineers role in the implementation of Industry 4.0 in Indian Engineering Industries, key ingredients of Industry 4.0 readiness model in Indian Engineering Industries and finally the need for a study on Industry 4.0 readiness model in Indian Engineering Industries is explicated.

Chapter 3 is dedicated to Materials and Methods. In this chapter, the materials and methods used in this study are described. The chapter starts with a brief introduction on materials and methods, followed by materials & methods used phase 1 which is a qualitative method using grounded theory methodology. Later, a detailed description as regards to sampling, data collection, interview protocol, data analysis, and ethical guidelines is given. Subsequently, in the chapter the phase 2 which is quantitative research for Industry 4.0 readiness model development is delineated with a specific focus on domain specification of the construct, development of an initial pool of items, purification of the measurement instrument, verification of dimensionality, construct validity assessment and reliability assessment.

Chapter 4 is committed to results. First, in the chapter, the results in phase 1 are described. The ten dimensions unearthed in phase 1 delineated along with arguments in extant literature. The formal definition of Industry 4.0 readiness model in Indian Engineering Industry is explicated based on the qualitative study. The phase 2 results are discussed phase-wise based on different phases of scale development

Chapter 5 is allocated for discussion. First, the results in phase 1 are discussed in detail. It is followed by the detailed discussion on phase 2 wherein the Industry 4.0 readiness model is described in detail.

Chapter 6 is apportioned for the conclusion, academic implication, the implication for the Indian Engineering Industries in terms of description, prescription, and comparison. Finally, the limitation of the study and scope for future work is also explicated.

8. LIST OF PUBLICATIONS OF THE RESEARCHER ON INDUSTRY 4.0 WHICH FORMS THE THEORETICAL UNDERPINNING OF THE PRESENT THESIS

The researcher than been actively researching on Industry 4.0 since 2016. The publication on Industry 4.0 done by the researcher as first author in various international journals is delineated below:

2018

1. Sony, M. (2018). Industry 4.0 and lean management: a proposed integration model and research propositions. *Production & Manufacturing Research*, 6(1), 416-432. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21693277.2018.1540949>

2019

2. Sony, M., & Naik, S. (2019). Key ingredients for evaluating Industry 4.0 readiness for organizations: a literature review. *Benchmarking: An International Journal*. Vol. 27 No. 7, pp. 2213-2232 <https://doi.org/10.1108/BIJ-09-2018-0284>
3. Sony, M., & Naik, S. S. (2019). Ten lessons for managers while implementing Industry 4.0. *IEEE Engineering Management Review*, 47(2), 45-52. DOI: [10.1109/EMR.2019.2913930](https://doi.org/10.1109/EMR.2019.2913930)

2020

4. Sony, M. (2020). Pros and cons of implementing Industry 4.0 for the organizations: a review and synthesis of evidence. *Production & Manufacturing Research*, 8(1), 244-272. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21693277.2020.1781705>
5. Sony, M., Antony, J., & Douglas, J. A. (2020). Essential ingredients for the implementation of Quality 4.0. *The TQM Journal*. Vol. 32 No. 4, pp. 779-793. <https://doi.org/10.1108/TQM-12-2019-0275>
6. Sony, M., & Naik, S. (2020). Industry 4.0 integration with socio-technical systems theory: A systematic review and proposed theoretical model. *Technology in Society*, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techsoc.2020.101248>

7. Sony, M. (2020). Design of cyber physical system architecture for industry 4.0 through lean six sigma: conceptual foundations and research issues. *Production & Manufacturing Research*, 8(1), 158-181. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21693277.2020.1774814>
8. Sony, M., & Naik, S. (2020). Critical factors for the successful implementation of Industry 4.0: a review and future research direction. *Production Planning & Control*, 31(10), 799-815. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09537287.2019.1691278>
9. Sony., Michael, & Aithal, P. S. (2020). Practical Lessons for Engineers to adapt towards Industry 4.0 in Indian Engineering Industries. *International Journal of Case Studies in Business, IT, and Education (IJCSBE)*, 4(2), 86-97. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4008814>
10. Sony., Michael, & Aithal, P. S. (2020). Transforming Indian Engineering Industries through Industry 4.0: An Integrative Conceptual Analysis. *International Journal of Applied Engineering and Management Letters (IJAEML)*, 4(2), 111-123. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4008834>.
11. Sony., Michael, & Aithal, P. S. (2020). Developing an Industry 4.0 Readiness Model for Indian Engineering Industries. *International Journal of Management, Technology, and Social Sciences (IJMTS)*, 5(2), 141-153. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4008855>

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